

Integrating Complex Event Processing and Machine Learning: an Intelligent Architecture for Detecting IoT Security Attacks

José Roldán^{a,*}, Juan Boubeta-Puig^b, José Luis Martínez^a, Guadalupe Ortiz^b

^a*Research Institute of Informatics (i3a), University of Castilla-La Mancha, Campus Universitario s/n, 02071, Albacete, Spain*

^b*Department of Computer Science and Engineering, University of Cadiz, Avda. de la Universidad de Cádiz 10, 11519 Puerto Real, Cádiz, Spain*

Abstract

The Internet of Things (IoT) is growing globally at a fast pace: people now find themselves surrounded by a variety of IoT devices such as smart-phones and wearables in their everyday lives. Additionally, smart environments, such as smart healthcare systems, smart industries and smart cities, benefit from sensors and actuators interconnected through the IoT. However, the increase in IoT devices has brought with it the challenge of promptly detecting and combating the cybersecurity attacks and threats that target them, including malware, privacy breaches and denial of service attacks, among others. To tackle this challenge, this paper proposes an intelligent architecture that integrates Complex Event Processing (CEP) technology and the Machine Learning (ML) paradigm in order to detect different types of IoT security attacks in real time. In particular, such an architecture is capable of easily managing event patterns whose conditions depend on values obtained by ML algorithms. Additionally, a model-driven graphical tool for security attack pattern definition and automatic code generation is provided, hiding all the complexity derived from implementation details from domain experts. The proposed architecture has been applied in the case of a healthcare IoT network to validate its ability to detect attacks made by malicious devices.

*Corresponding author. Tel.: (+34) 967599200

Email addresses: jose.roldan@uclm.es (José Roldán), juan.boubeta@uca.es (Juan Boubeta-Puig), joseluis.martinez@uclm.es (José Luis Martínez), guadalupe.ortiz@uca.es (Guadalupe Ortiz)

The results obtained demonstrate that this architecture satisfactorily fulfils its objectives.

Keywords: Complex event processing, Machine learning, Software architecture, Intelligent decision making, Internet of Things, Security attack

1. Introduction

The Internet of Things (IoT) is expanding globally, providing diverse benefits in nearly every aspect of our lives, such as health-care, entertainment, transportation, industry, smart cities and even our daily routine. Every single device is able to connect to the Internet and communicate with the web or mobile applications, or even share data with other objects (Atzori et al., 2010). However, it is important to bear in mind that these autonomous objects are provided with limited features, such as small memories, a low bandwidth communication channel, a small processor, and low cost sensors or actuators, so although this confers a form of intelligence (smart objects), it is limited.

Nowadays, the trend for the IoT market is for continued growth, as indicated by CISCO, and it is expected to be worth around 14.4 trillion dollars between 2013 and 2022 (Raynovich, 2017). Nevertheless, emerging IoT technologies face various security attacks and threats, which include malware, privacy breaches, Denial of Service (DoS) attacks, security vulnerabilities with available exploits, and disruption of IoT networks (Andrea et al., 2015). Taking into account the inherent computational limitations of IoT devices in addition to their vulnerabilities, as well as their expected proliferation worldwide, both the risks and the projected global impact of connecting IoT devices to the network in any modern environment become evident. Not only do IoT devices have to be protected, but also the communications between them: huge volumes of data can be exchanged between devices and between the latter and servers or consumers, and the compromised availability, integrity, or confidentiality of these data can have a great impact.

In this field, in recent years, Machine Learning (ML) has been used to detect anomalous behaviour in the IoT (Buczak and Guven, 2016; Gharibian and Ghorbani, 2007; Meidan et al., 2017). Basically, the proposals consist in trying to train a model to understand the normal behaviour of an infrastructure or system and to detect when a new security issue occurs. However, when testing the model, numerous false positives —considering false posi-

tives as legit packets detected as anomalies— can appear until the model is correctly adjusted. As an example, a pure ML-based Intrusion Detection System (IDS) usually fails when the scenario is very complex, producing many false positives. Therefore, there is a gap in this field which has not yet been covered: there are no tools or approaches which enable the prediction and detection of unknown attacks in the field of the IoT, bearing in mind that in this scenario resources may be limited and it is essential to detect such attacks in real time. In addition, since the handling of IoT devices is not limited to specially qualified users, as nowadays any citizen with a basic knowledge of the technology can install and use such devices, the tools that detect attacks should provide a graphical interface that allows such users to benefit from the knowledge of a computer expert.

In order to cover this gap, we propose to use Complex Event Processing (CEP) technology in conjunction with ML techniques. CEP is a technology that is designed to process, analyze and correlate big amounts of real-time data produced by IoT devices and systems with the aim of promptly detecting situations of interest in multiple domains (Garcia-de Prado et al., 2017; Kousiouris et al., 2018; Terroso-Saenz et al., 2019). Even though CEP has demonstrated benefits such as its ability for efficiently processing network security data on the fly without being previously stored (Gad et al., 2012, 2013), only some isolated works make use of this technology for detecting security attacks and threats (Gad et al., 2013; Vegh and Miclea, 2016).

Considering such benefits provided by CEP and ML, in this paper, we propose an intelligent architecture that integrates both CEP and ML in order to promptly detect IoT security attacks by defining event patterns whose conditions depend on values of the network packets predicted by ML algorithms. More specifically, this proposal is based on our previously proposed Event-Driven Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA 2.0) (Boubeta-Puig et al., 2015), which has been extended with ML capabilities and then applied to the IoT security domain.

In such an architecture one of the key parts is the Enterprise Service Bus (ESB): the ESB is the middleware that makes it possible to create the data connection between IoT networks and both the CEP engine and ML algorithms, as well as to allow the CEP engine to communicate with data consumers such as trusted computers, email servers and alert databases. In this way, the CEP engine can receive both network packet events as a result of preprocessing IoT sensing data, and prediction network packet events generated upon training ML algorithm execution. By analyzing and correlating

these events through the use of event patterns, the CEP engine is capable of detecting IoT security attacks in real time, as well as notifying them to data consumers through the ESB. Thanks to the integration of the ESB and the ML algorithms with the MEdit4CEP model-driven approach (Boubeta-Puig et al., 2015), security domain experts can graphically define which types of security attack must be analyzed and prevented, without having advanced knowledge about CEP, ML or IoT networks. The graphical security attack models are then automatically transformed into implementation code, which is automatically deployed in the proposed architecture at runtime. Therefore, the main contribution of this paper is an SOA 2.0 integrating CEP, ML, IoT and MEdit4CEP for detecting IoT security attacks and threats in a user-friendly way.

To sum up, the main contributions of this paper are twofold: firstly, the integration of an SOA 2.0 architecture with ML techniques which facilitates the real-time detection and prevention of security attacks in the IoT; secondly, the extension of MEdit4CEP to support the graphical definition of the security attacks to be detected and prevented in the new enhanced architecture. Furthermore, in order to validate our proposal, the architecture has been applied to an IoT network prototype constructed in a hospital with the aim of detecting attacks made by a malicious device. The results confirm that the integration of CEP with ML is powerful in this realistic scenario, and that this architecture works effectively when using a model that can be adapted to the context of the scenario in question. Since a model can be defined with many layers similarly to those proposed by the Open System Interconnections (OSI) and Transmission Control Protocol(TCP)/Internet Protocol (IP) models (Rondeau et al., 2019), our proposal is able to adapt to any layers from physical to enterprise network ones. To address it, the only requirement is to redefine the packet features.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 explains the basic concepts needed to understand the work presented. Section 3 deals with the main components of the proposed architecture integrating CEP and ML. Then, Section 4 presents the application of the architecture to detect IoT security attacks. Section 5 shows the results obtained, while Section 6 describes the related work. Finally, Section 7 draws some conclusions and describes lines for future research.

2. Background

The subject matters relevant to the content of this paper is introduced in this section.

2.1. *Complex event processing*

CEP is a technology that allows the capture, analysis and correlation of large amounts of simple events with the aim of detecting relevant situations in a particular domain (Luckham, 2012). Captured events are data that, for instance, flow through information systems or are provided by IoT devices, among others. They are called simple events because they are usually raw data. From the processing of such simple events, we can infer information with a greater semantic knowledge in real time, therefore obtaining the so-called complex events.

Thus, in a given context, we will be interested in detecting relevant situations according to the domain in question, that is, complex events. To do this, we will have to define a series of event patterns that specify the conditions that must be met by input simple events to detect such situations. These patterns are defined in a CEP, which is a software used to match these patterns over the incoming event streams, and capable of analyzing the data and highlighting detected situations of interest in real time. Each CEP engine has its own specific Event Processing Language (EPL) for the pattern definition.

The main advantage of CEP compared with other traditional event analysis software is the ability to process large amounts of data and notify the interested parties of the detected situations of interest in real time, thus considerably reducing the latency in the decision-making process, and therefore giving a competitive advantage to the user in question.

2.2. *Event-driven service-oriented architecture*

SOA 2.0, also called ED-SOA, evolved from the traditional Service-Oriented Architecture (SOA). While in SOA communications are performed following the request/response paradigm (Papazoglou, 2012), in SOA 2.0 communications are performed in reaction to events occurring in the system (Taylor, 2009), i.e., events trigger asynchronous messages that are sent to independent software components. To achieve this integration, a software abstraction layer is required that is capable of integrating various heterogeneous data sources with the software components to be invoked. These functionalities

are offered by an ESB (Papazoglou and Heuvel, 2006), which permits interoperability among several communication protocols and heterogeneous data sources and sinks. In addition to being in charge of transforming messages to the necessary protocols and their correct routing, the ESB can provide a series of added functions such as security support, monitoring, auditing, and many others, depending on the particular ESB.

In this way, through the use of ED-SOA and an ESB, applications and services can respond quickly to asynchronous events and allow server and client to be completely decoupled. Despite all the advantages provided by SOA 2.0, this type of architecture might not be ideal for analyzing and correlating big amounts of data in terms of events. Therefore, we have integrated SOA 2.0 with CEP technology in order to be able not only to respond quickly to events, but also to process, analyze, and correlate these events in order to promptly detect situations of interest for a particular domain.

2.3. MEdit4CEP

As mentioned above, the integration of SOA 2.0 with CEP considerably improves real-time decision-making. In order to benefit from such integration, we need to accurately define event patterns that allow the detection of the situations of interest based on the incoming event stream. This is undoubtedly the task of the domain expert, who does not necessarily have to be an expert in software programming. Therefore, we must provide experts with a graphical tool to help them define the patterns correctly. MEdit4CEP (Boubeta-Puig et al., 2015) was designed and implemented for this purpose.

Thus, MEdit4CEP is a model-driven solution for real-time decision making in SOA 2.0. whose main aim is to facilitate the definition of event patterns for domain experts. This solution provides a graphical modeling editor for CEP domain definition and a graphical modeling editor for event pattern definition. It also provides automatic code generation and deployment from the patterns modeled by the domain expert. In particular, MEdit4CEP currently generates the pattern code in Esper EPL, the language supported by the Esper CEP engine (EsperTech, 2019a), and deploys the code in the engine at runtime.

2.4. Machine learning

ML techniques refer to the study of algorithms and systems that are capable of learning or acquiring knowledge from experiences. ML uses statistics

with different kinds of algorithms to solve a problem by studying and analyzing data. Due to its success, ML has been used in an extensive range of applications including search engines, medical diagnosis, Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) sequence classification, and object recognition in computer vision, and, more recently, it has been applied to improve network security in terms of authentication, access control, anti-jamming offloading, DoS and malware detection (Ozay et al., 2016; Narudin et al., 2016; Buczak and Guven, 2016; Tan et al., 2011).

In general, there are two types of ML algorithms: supervised learning and unsupervised learning. On the one hand, supervised learning uses data samples with known measurements and class membership to create a set of rules to classify data samples with known measurements and assign class membership. On the other hand, unsupervised learning does not require labeled data, as in the supervised learning, and investigates the similarity between the unlabeled data to cluster them into different groups (Al-Garadi et al., 2018).

The ML techniques used in this work are based on supervised learning. In particular, this paper uses a Linear Regression (Miheșcu, 2011) method to model the relationship between a scalar response and many explanatory variables (multiple linear regression). The proposed model can be used to fit a predictive model generated from an observed dataset of values extracted from a regular network scenario. The key point is identifying the information that can be used to build the predictive model. After developing such a model, if additional values of the explanatory variables are collected without an associated response value, the fitted model can be used to make a prediction of the response: normal behaviour or anomalous behaviour. This paper also uses the Support Vector Regression (SVR) regressor. Note that the comparison of ML algorithms is out of the scope of this paper. We are aiming to show that our proposal can be adapted to any model; we use the same features set and a linear kernel (Basak et al., 2007).

In particular, we will use a novel architecture (rules with CEP together with linear or SVR regression) and define manual patterns for common attacks, as port scans, and linear regression in conjunction with CEP against attacks over Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT). Although we can use CEP together with linear regression against common attacks, our goal is to show the advantage of our architecture against unknown attacks (or attacks that we have not been included in our model). Therefore, the use of CEP in conjunction with regression (linear or SVR in this case) is used

to detect MQTT attacks, when we do not know the expected value of the attack packets. With this architecture we have a twofold benefit: on the one hand, we can predict attacks that we do not know in advance; on the other we can create patterns that detect well-known attacks.

2.5. IoT network communication

The IoT (Gubbi et al., 2013) is a powerful paradigm in which many objects are able to obtain relevant information and communicate with each other.

Although the IoT allows us to upgrade interaction with our surroundings, it creates new challenges to be overcome, such as constrained devices, dynamic networks, battery autonomy and heterogeneous protocols. In the field of security management, all these challenges might be a handicap, so we need new approaches and tools to improve the current situation. As an example, the integration of the IoT paradigm with CEP technology allows us to extract important information, understand the situation, act accordingly and improve our living and working conditions (Boubeta-Puig et al., 2014).

MQTT is a very common protocol used in the IoT (OASIS, 2019). MQTT offers a small overhead (2 bytes from its fixed header, normally). Moreover, MQTT is a binary protocol that reduces the overhead compared with other application layer protocols. It is a publish/subscribe-based protocol in which a server (there can be more than one), known as the message broker, manages the information flow organized in a hierarchy of topics. Each client can be a subscriber and a publisher simultaneously. When a publisher device needs to send new information, it publishes a topic containing the information in the broker, then the broker distributes this information to all subscriber devices, which have been previously subscribed to this topic in particular. Although there are other IoT protocols, we use MQTT because it is consolidated and widely used. In any case, our solution can be adapted for different technologies and protocols.

2.6. Security attacks

Security attacks, which can be classified as critical or soft, are a constant threat for every system. Therefore, taking actions is necessary to avoid unrecoverable problems that could affect our confidentiality, integrity or availability. IoT systems have several constraints, such as a small memory, a

dynamic and heterogeneous network and a limited battery, that prevent developers from using a usual security setup. Therefore, the actions for this kind of system need to be reconsidered.

A very common attack against IoT systems consists of producing a DoS of the system. There are many methods to perform this, such as, for example, the Mirai attack, which consisted in gaining access to the system using common credentials against Telnet, Secure Shell (SSH) or other services, thus allowing the attacker to take control of the device. The attacker, through the use of a big number of devices, usually uses this method to flood a target, which is the victim.

The first step before attacking the target is usually to carry out port scanning. This is not an attack per se but it makes it possible to be aware of the open ports. The attacker can craft and send packets and interpret the responses to perform the port scans.

Since DoS and port scans are very common, we have considered both of them in our application scenario.

3. Proposed architecture

In this section, our proposed architecture is described. This architecture is composed of two distinct parts. The first part includes the processes to be executed at runtime (top half of Figure 1), i.e. the behaviour of our system, whereas the second part covers the processes that take place at design time (bottom half of Figure 1).

3.1. Runtime Architecture

In particular, the runtime part is based on an SOA 2.0, which is responsible for: (1) capturing the real-time IoT data produced by data sources; (2) processing, analyzing and correlating such data reached by the ESB; and (3) acting and making decisions about the situations of interest detected, as well as notifying data sinks of them.

In this architecture, IoT networks are used as data sources. IoT networks are composed of several IoT nodes connected to a message broker, which is in charge of sending all raw sensor data to the ESB through the MQTT protocol, as well as generating the raw sensor data for training purpose in an isolated scenario without any security attacks.

The ESB receives the real-time raw sensor data, preprocesses them and transforms them into a common format of network events. Additionally, the

Figure 1: The proposed architecture for detecting IoT security attacks.

ESB receives the training raw sensor data and preprocesses them to make them consumable for our training ML algorithm (linear regression or SVR in this case). Then, the ESB produces a trained model, which will be used to generate *NetworkPrediction* events containing a timestamp, a predicted value (of packet length in this case) and a margin where a normal value should be. Each packet in the network will have an associated *NetworkPrediction* event. Note that the difference between a training packet and a normal packet is that the training packet is used during the training stage, while the normal packet is predicted by the trained model.

We should point out that the values of the key features (features essential for detecting a specific scenario) for validating a legitimate packet are not necessarily fixed, as the domain expert can use the predictor and generate a dynamic predictor with the knowledge obtained for a legit scenario. If a packet's real value obtained from a predicted feature is outside a prediction

bound for this kind of packet, the system will detect it. Since the predictor has the ability to adapt to different cases, it works correctly not only with homogeneous scenarios but also with heterogeneous ones.

Afterwards, the CEP engine, which has been integrated with the ESB, receives both network events and *NetworkPrediction* events, and it also analyzes and correlates these events in order to detect and predict security attacks (complex events) in real time, according to the event patterns previously defined and deployed in the engine.

Upon complex event detection, the decision-process component will promptly notify the data sinks (trusted computers, email servers and alerts databases, among others) previously subscribed to this type of complex events.

3.2. Design time architecture

The design time part of the architecture is based on the MEdit4CEP model-driven approach (Boubeta-Puig et al., 2015), whose main aim is the definition of high-level models, which are understandable to any user. These models are automatically transformed into code that is executable in the CEP engine and the decision-process component located in the ESB.

As shown in the bottom half of Figure 1, the design time part includes the domain expert, representing people who possess a wide knowledge of network security and so understand the normal behaviour of the system to protect, but do not necessarily have knowledge of CEP or ML. These experts are suitable candidates to accurately define the CEP domain composed of the network event and *NetworkPrediction* event types with their properties, as well as to graphically define the security attack event patterns through a graphical tool, hiding them from the implementation details.

The steps involved for the definition and code generation of the IoT security domain and event patterns are as follows:

1. The domain expert creates a graphical IoT security domain model from scratch, defining event types with their properties.
2. Once the domain model is defined, the editor will be responsible for its syntactic validation. If it is not valid, the domain expert will be advised to correct the detected errors. This model will then be saved.
3. The domain expert will create security attack pattern models. To do this, the graphical editor will be customized with the previously defined domain model. One should take into account that the defined patterns might include the values obtained by the ML algorithm dynamically.

4. Once pattern models have been defined, the editor will be responsible for their validation. If any of them are invalid, the user will be asked to correct the detected errors. These models will then be saved.
5. Each of these pattern models will be automatically transformed into code, which consists of both the EPL the code implementing the conditions to be satisfied so that the CEP engine can detect the security attacks, and code of actions to be carried out in the ESB when detecting prospective security attacks.
6. The event pattern code generated will be added to the CEP engine while the action code generated will be added to the decision-process component in the ESB at runtime.

It is worth noting that the design time part of the architecture provides two advantages. Firstly, the use of MEdit4CEP allows the domain expert to easily design the IoT security domain model and security attack patterns without requiring any programming language. Secondly, the connection with a predictor makes it possible to model dynamic patterns, in which the definition of some event properties depends on the values automatically computed by the predictor. We use the term **dynamic** patterns because our predictor computes the estimated value for a legitimate packet by using the features of these packets, and the patterns make use of such prediction values. Therefore, the combination of MEdit4CEP and the predictor makes our architecture user-friendly, customized and adaptable to new attacks and security scenarios.

The main advantage of our proposal against existing rule-based IDS is that our architecture is able to detect attacks that have not been defined in our model, as explained in Section 5. So, we could define an “unknown attack pattern” to be triggered when the incoming packets contain uncommon values. Additionally, this could be used for a smart definition of thresholds for known attacks, such as a DoS. Therefore, our architecture is also very versatile.

4. Applying the architecture to detect IoT security attacks

The aim of this section is to provide a real-world scenario in which our proposed architecture can be applied in order to check that it works correctly.

In particular, we have applied our architecture to an IoT network prototype constructed in a hospital. This network is composed of noise sensors

located in different rooms of the hospital. The measurements taken by the sensors could be used to detect noise levels in real time as well as to notify nurses when a noise level is too high in a particular room. In this way, a nurse could go to this room as soon as possible to recommend that the patient’s visitors speak more quietly, thus improving the patient’s well-being.

In this section, we focus on detecting IoT security attacks in this network by using our proposed architecture. Note that the detection of noise level is beyond the scope of this paper.

4.1. Data sources

To test our proposal we designed and constructed such an IoT network as the data source for our architecture.

Figure 2 depicts the network topology, which is composed of three legitimate devices, a broker and a malicious device for implementing attacks. The devices use the MQTT protocol to share information with the broker; in this case, they share information about noise.

Figure 2: IoT network topology for the real-world scenario.

Although this network is simple, it is effective in illustrating the proposed architecture. Note that the same network topology could be applied to other application domains in which devices share other types of information.

Additionally, this IoT network has been emulated with Virtual Box (Oracle, 2019), obtaining similar results to those when using real devices. Specifically, an application in which each device generates random numbers and

publishes them in its own topic has been emulated. We have used virtual machines because these make it possible to modify the set up quickly and change the test cases easily.

4.2. ESB

The functionalities provided by the ESB (see Section 3) have been implemented by using Mule ESB 3.9 (MuleSoft, 2019). Our ESB application is composed of four data flows, as detailed in the following paragraphs.

The first data flow is responsible for gathering the raw sensor data through the MQTT protocol endpoint, transforming them into network event format and then sending the events to the Esper 7.1 CEP engine (EsperTech, 2019a).

The second data flow is in charge of predicting events from the training sensor data received through another MQTT protocol endpoint. To do this, we have implemented a predictor in Python 3.6 (Python Software Foundation, 2019) using the Numpy (NumPy, 2019), Scikit-learn (Scikit-learn, 2019) and Pandas (Pandas, 2019) libraries. This predictor uses traces of packages captured using Wireshark (Wireshark, 2019) in the broker to fit the model. Since Pandas works easily with data in the Comma-Separated Values (CSV) format and Wireshark makes it possible to export the captured data in CSV, the predictor also works with this format. Figure 3 illustrates the dataflow scheme. Note that, if needed, Wireshark could be replaced by another packet analyzer because our architecture is entirely modular.

Figure 3: Dataflow scheme.

In particular, our predictor currently works with linear regression (or SVR algorithms in some experiments), which are essential to fit our model

by using a *normal case* in which the system works correctly without attacks. Additionally, we have defined port scans and attacks (see Section 4.5) to test both our predictor and the system behaviour when it suffers an attack. We should point out that, although we have used linear regression and SVR because of their suitability for our features, other ML methods could be used in our architecture if necessary.

The third data flow is responsible for both receiving the Esper EPL pattern code automatically generated by MEdit4CEP and deploying it in the Esper CEP engine, while the fourth data flow receives the action code generated by MEdit4CEP and makes the decisions about which data sinks will be notified about the situations of interest detected in real time.

4.3. Data sinks

Three types of data sinks have been considered in this architecture: (1) alert databases, on which the detected situations of interest are stored; (2) emails with their body containing the description of the detected situations to be notified to the subscribed users; and (3) trusted computers in charge of displaying such situations on dashboards in real time.

Since our architecture is flexible, other data sinks could be included in the future, according to the domain expert's needs.

4.4. IoT security domain

The *IoTSecurity* domain has been graphically modeled by using MEdit4CEP, as shown in Figure 4. This domain is composed of two types of event types: *NetworkPacket* and *NetworkPrediction*.

In particular, *NetworkPacket* defines the event information required for traces of packets captured by network protocol analyzers, such as Wireshark. As depicted in Figure 4, the event properties have been modeled according to the OSI reference model (Zimmermann, 1980), i.e. grouping the properties by OSI layers. Therefore, *NetworkPacket* contains the time (in epoch format) at which the packet is captured, the packet length in bytes, the packet info that is defined by Wireshark and depends on the protocol, and also the following nested properties: *networkInterface*, *internet*, *TCP*, User Datagram Protocol (*UDP*) and *MQTT*.

The *networkInterface* property is composed of:

- *sourceMAC*: sender's MAC address.
- *destinationMAC*: receiver's MAC address.

Figure 4: IoT security domain modeled with MEdit4CEP.

The *internet* property is composed of:

- *sourceIP*: sender's IP address.
- *destinationIP*: receiver's IP address.
- *protocol*: upper layer protocol.

The *TCP* property is composed of:

- *sourcePort*: TCP port of the sender device.
- *destinationPort*: TCP port of the receiver device.
- *flags*: flags provided by the TCP protocol indicating the following actions:
 1. Synchronization (*SYN*): used for connection establishment. It is only used in the first packet from the sender and the receiver.
 2. Acknowledgement (*ACK*): used to acknowledge the packets that have been received.
 3. Push (*PSH*): used to send a packet immediately to the application layer, without requiring the receiver to wait for the maximum segment size buffering the packet.
 4. Urgent (*URG*): allows marking packets as urgent, these being processed first.
 5. Finish (*FIN*): used to request TCP to terminate the connection gracefully without data loss.
 6. Reset (*RST*): used to request TCP to terminate the connection abruptly —data loss could occur.

- *calculatedWindowSize*: indicates the size of the connection window.

The *UDP* property is composed of:

- *sourcePort*: UDP port of the sender device.
- *destinationPort*: UDP port of the receiver device.

The *MQTT* property is composed of:

- *flags*: these indicate the kind of MQTT packet —there being 14 different packets, but their study is beyond the scope of this paper. Also, the publish packet provides three more flags, namely:
 1. Duplicate delivery of a publish Control Packet (*DUP*): indicates whether a publish message has been resent. This happens when there is a QoS greater than 0 and there is no ACK for the original packet.
 2. Publish Quality of Service (*QoS*): indicates the quality of service level. Three levels are represented by using 2 bits. Level 0 fulfils the *at most once* scheme; in this level there is no resending. Level 1 ensures that the packet meets the *at least once* schema, but duplicated packets at the receiver could exist. Level 2 ensures that the packet fulfils the *exactly once* schema.
 3. Publish Retain flag (*RETAIN*): This flag makes setting a fixed message (only one) per topic possible. In this way, when a new client subscribes to the topic, it will receive the retained message. Each client can manage the message as needed, although this flag is usually used to update the state of new devices.
- *message*: the message contained in the MQTT packet.
- *topic*: topic's name.
- *messageLength*: MQTT packet's length.
- *frameCounter*: the number of fragmented packets that make up a full packet.

In addition, the *NetworkPrediction* event type contains the time (in epoch format) at which the prediction is calculated, the *packetLengthPredict* property, which represents the value predicted by our predictor based on the destination port, protocol, frame counter and calculated windows size, and the *packetLengthPredictSquaredError* property, which indicates the squared error committed by our predictor in the training stage.

4.5. Security attack patterns

Once the *IoTSecurity* domain has been designed, the event pattern editor is automatically reconfigured for this domain, i.e., the event types modeled in the domain are included in the tool palette of the editor.

In order to validate our proposal, we consider the modeling of the following five patterns of attacks, in which a malicious device generates attacks against the MQTT network.

4.5.1. *TCP/SYN port scan*

In the *TCP/SYN port scan* attack, the malicious device sends a round of 10 or more TCP packets with SYN flag to 3 or more different ports of the broker in 1 s. If the port is open, the broker sends a SYN/ACK packet, otherwise it sends an RST packet.

By using the MEdit4CEP tool, this attack has been modeled as two patterns. The *SrcDst_TCP_1s_Batch* pattern (see Figure 5a) is responsible for obtaining all the network packet events whose protocol is TCP and whose flags are 0x002 in 1-s batch windows; then, the number of packet events as well as the number of distinct TCP destination ports in every batch window are calculated and grouped by source IP and destination IP. This information, together with the current timestamp, the source IP and the destination IP, is inserted into complex events named *SrcDst_TCP_1s_Batch*. Once this pattern has been syntactically validated, the Esper EPL code, which is illustrated in Figure 5b, is automatically generated by MEdit4CEP.

Afterwards, for each *SrcDst_TCP_1s_Batch* complex event created, the *TCP_SYN* pattern modeled (see Figure 6a) checks whether both its count property is greater or equal to 10 and the destination port distinct count is greater or equal to 3. Once this pattern has been syntactically validated, the Esper EPL code, which is depicted in Figure 6b, is automatically generated.

4.5.2. *UDP port scan*

In the *UDP port scan* attack, the malicious device sends a round of 10 or more empty UDP packets to 3 or more different ports of the broker in 5 s. If the broker sends any response, then the port is open, but if the broker does not send a response, the port could be open. If the broker sends ICMP unreachable, the port should be closed. And if it sends another error (not unreachable), the port should be filtered.

This attack has been modeled in a similar way to the *TCP/SYN port scan* attack, but replacing the 1-s batch window by a 5-s one, and the TCP protocol property by the UDP one. The modeled *SrcDst_UDP_5s_Batch* and the *UDP_Port_Scan* patterns are shown in Figure 7a and Figure 7b, respectively.

(a) Pattern model.

```

@Name("SrcDst_TCP_1s_Batch")
@Tag(name="domainName", value="IoTSecurity")
insert into SrcDst_TCP_1s_Batch
select current_timestamp() as timestamp,
       a1.internet.sourceIP as sourceIP,
       a1.internet.destinationIP as destinationIP,
       count(a1.internet.sourceIP) as count,
       count(distinct a1.TCP.destinationPort) as destinationPortDistinctCount
from pattern [(every a1 = NetworkPacket((a1.internet.protocol = 'TCP' and
a1.TCP.flags = '0x002')))] win:time_batch(1 seconds)
group by a1.internet.sourceIP, a1.internet.destinationIP

```

(b) Pattern implementation in Esper EPL.

Figure 5: *SrcDst_TCP_1s_Batch* pattern modeled and generated with MEdit4CEP.

(a) Pattern model.

```

@Name("TCP_SYN")
@Tag(name="domainName", value="IoTSecurity")
insert into TCP_SYN
select a1.timestamp as timestamp,
      a1.sourceIP as sourceIP,
      a1.destinationIP as destinationIP
from pattern [(every a1 = SrcDst_TCP_1s_Batch((a1.count >= 10 and
      a1.destinationPortDistinctCount >= 3)))]

```

(b) Pattern implementation in Esper EPL.

Figure 6: *TCP_SYN* pattern modeled and generated with MEdit4CEP.

4.5.3. Xmas port scan

In the *Xmas port scan* attack, the malicious device sends a round of 10 or more TCP packets with PSH, FIN and URG flags to 2 or more different ports of the broker in 1 s. If the broker does not respond, the port should be open or filtered. If the broker sends an RST packet, it should be closed. If the broker sends an ICMP unreachable error, it should be filtered. Note that although this attack/scan does not work frequently, it is useful for evaluating our proposal.

This attack has been modeled in a similar way to the *TCP/SYN port scan* attack, but replacing the *0x002* TCP flag property by *0x029*, and updating the condition of destination port distinct count to greater or equal to 2, instead of 3. The modeled *SrcDst_Xmas_1s_Batch* and the *Xmas_Scan*

patterns are shown in Figure 8a and Figure 8b, respectively.

(a) *SrcDst_UDP_5s_Batch* pattern model.

(b) *UDP_Port_Scan* pattern model.

Figure 7: *SrcDst_UDP_5s_Batch* and *UDP_Port_Scan* patterns modeled with MEdit4CEP.

4.5.4. DoS with big messages

In the *DoS with big messages* attack, the malicious device publishes a heavy message to the broker, producing a DoS.

It is worth noting that this attack has been defined as a *dynamic* pattern (see Figure 9a) through the combining of CEP and ML. As can be seen, this pattern searches MQTT publish messages (publish is defined by flag *0x30*) that are beyond the upper or lower limit. We do not need to define the limit, since our regressor does it. Once the regressor has been trained with a part of the legitimate case (the normal MQTT case), it can predict a value for each MQTT packet by using its features, thus generating a *NetworkPrediction* event. This pattern is automatically transformed into Esper EPL code, as shown in Figure 9b.

4.5.5. Anomaly

The *Anomaly* pattern's goal is to detect unknown attacks. This makes it possible to detect attacks which we have not modeled and our predictor does not know.

This pattern has been also defined as a *dynamic* pattern (see Figure 10a). As can be seen, this pattern is triggered when a packet contains a non-known protocol (a non-known protocol is any protocol that we do not have in our normal scenario). This is also triggered when a packet has an anomalous length value. Note that we have used this value because it is linearly and directly correlated with many important features to detect anomalies (see Figure 11) and we make use of the same predictor used in the DoS pattern. It is important to highlight that this pattern can be defined in many domains by adapting the features and the model.

This pattern is automatically transformed into Esper EPL code, as shown in Figure 10b.

4.5.6. Discwave attack

In the *DoS with big messages* attack, the malicious device sends many connects commands with different identifications (MQTT broker uses the id to identify each client) against the broker. This attack can be very dangerous in many systems, where the broker is configured for expel devices with old connections (when a new device with the same id sends a connect command). It can shut down all the MQTT network. Notice that this attack is very different from the DoS attack.

(a) *SrcDst_Xmas_1s_Batch* pattern model.

(b) *Xmas_Scan* pattern model.

Figure 8: *SrcDst_Xmas_1s_Batch* and *Xmas_Scan* patterns modeled with MEdit4CEP.

(a) Pattern model.

```

@Name("MQTT_BigMsg_DoS")
@Tag(name="domainName", value="IoTSecurity")
insert into MQTT_BigMsg_DoS
select current_timestamp() as timestamp, a1.internet.destinationIP as destinationIP
from pattern [((every a1 = NetworkPacket((a1.internet.protocol = 'MQTT' and
a1.MQTT.flags = '0x30')) -> a2 = NetworkPrediction((a2.timestamp = a1.timestamp
and (a2.packetLengthPredict < (a1.packetLength -
a2.packetLengthPredictSquaredError) or a2.packetLengthPredict >
(a1.packetLength + a2.packetLengthPredictSquaredError))))))]

```

(b) Pattern implementation in Esper EPL.

Figure 9: *MQTT_BigMsg_DoS* pattern modeled and generated with MEdit4CEP.

(a) Pattern model.

```

@Name("Anomaly")
@Tag(name="domainName", value="IoTSecurity")
insert into Anomaly
select current_timestamp() as timestamp, a2.internet.destinationIP as destinationIP
from pattern [(
  (every a1 = NetworkPacket(a1.internet.protocol != 'MQTT' and
    a1.internet.protocol != 'TCP' and a1.internet.protocol != 'ARP' and
    a1.internet.protocol != 'DHCP' and a1.internet.protocol != 'MDNS' and
    a1.internet.protocol != 'NTP' and a1.internet.protocol != 'ICMPv6' and
    a1.internet.protocol != 'IGMPv3' and a1.internet.protocol != 'DNS' and
    a1.internet.protocol != 'ICMP' and a1.internet.protocol != 'UDP'))
  or ((every a2 = NetworkPacket((a2.internet.protocol = 'MQTT' or
    a2.internet.protocol = 'TCP')) -> a3 = NetworkPrediction((a3.timestamp = a2.timestamp
    and (a3.packetLengthPredict < (a2.packetLength -
    a3.packetLengthPredictSquaredError) or a3.packetLengthPredict >
    (a2.packetLength + a3.packetLengthPredictSquaredError)))))))]

```

(b) Pattern implementation in Esper EPL.

Figure 10: *Anomaly* pattern model and generated with MEDIT4CEP.

4.5.7. Subfuzzing attack

Subfuzzing attack has been designed to map the topics hierarchy when MQTT wildcards are disabled. The wildcards allow us to subscribe multiple topics simultaneously. The attack is quite simple, only a list of possible topics is required. The attacker sends multiple topics subscription attempts with different topic names. If it receives a *suback* packet, then it knows that the topic exists.

4.6. Mirai

Mirai is a well-known malware, although our predictor has not been trained with it. In this case, we try to detect the first Mirai stage (we want detect the attack before it can infect us). This first stage sends multiple usernames and passwords over Telnet to gain access, after that it runs (or downloads) the malware payload.

5. Experiments and Results

This section describes and discusses the experiments performed and the results obtained in order to demonstrate the viability of the proposed architecture for detecting IoT attacks. In particular, we have conducted three types of experiments.

First, we have conducted a features selection process, which allows us to find representative features. Moreover, in this case, it can be used to determine the correct ML model.

Second, we have modeled the events patterns for detecting the well-known attacks such as —TCP, UDP and Xmas port scans (see Sections 4.5.1, 4.5.2 and 4.5.3) and also DoS attack (see Section 4.5.4)— against our network (see Section 4.1). The simpler port scans are modeled by using the CEP engine without the predictor and the DoS attack by using a linear regression predictor to determine the threshold depending of the understanding of the network.

Third, departing from the model latter, it has been also modeled the event pattern Anomaly (see Section 4.5.5) against the broker by making use of the CEP engine together with the linear regression predictor (the same used in DoS pattern). Furthermore, in order to demonstrate that other predictors are also valid, the SVR predictor has been also include in the experiments.

Finally, in order to check the Anomaly detection pattern, we have included in the network three new attacks which have not been identified before

by the proposed model such as –Discwave, Subfuzzing and Mirai (depicted in Sections 4.5.6, 4.5.7 and 4.6)–. All of them are detected by the model as anomalies and, after an analysis, they can be included and modeled as new patterns to further classify them in the future.

All these patterns have been validated and automatically transformed into Esper EPL code. Then, this code has been deployed in the CEP engine at runtime, producing the following results that are compared in Section 5.5.

5.1. Feature selection

The set of features have been selected with a simple and solid criteria proposed by KDD99 (Kayacik et al., 2005) (those which are adaptable to a MQTT scenario) and we have also added features extracted from MQTT. The MQTT features have been selected heuristically; although, it is adaptable to any protocol. We have used Extremely Randomized Trees with datasets composed by MQTT regular traffic, background and malicious attacks over MQTT (brute force, broker spoofing and malformed MQTT packets). This allows us measure the importance of each feature.

As we can see in Figure 11, our features fits perfectly in this domain. It is important to highlight that we have not used particular datasets to fit the feature selection process or system evaluation.

Figure 11: Feature importance.

We emphasize that some features are correlated with others ones; for example, packet length is correlated with others features such as calculated window size, protocol used and the information field. Thus, packet length feature is linearly and directly correlated with other features and fits well with a linear regressor and it is useful to detect unknown attacks.

Obviously, in other cases we will need a more complex predictor with other features, but this is not a limitation for our architecture: the modular architecture allow us to modify any component easily.

5.2. CEP engine without the predictor

As Figure 12 shows, there are 2 complex events that have detected UDP port scans. However, why are there only 2 complex events although the scan is prolonged in time? This has happened because UDP/SCAN is a very slow scan and the pattern conditions require that there are at least 10 packets in 5 seconds. These conditions are satisfied only in the first part of our scan, which generated several packets in few seconds, as illustrated in this figure. After that, there is a slower flow of UDP packets, and no more complex events are detected.

Similarly to the UDP port scan, the results of the Xmas port scan (see Figure 13) show that, at the beginning, the TCP flow is more dense.

Figure 14 shows the detection of TCP/SYN port scans. As can be seen, TCP/SYN is very fast (less than 0.5 seconds). Therefore, only one complex event has been triggered after finishing the full scan.

With theses experiments we confirm that CEP is a suitable technology to detect such port scanning patterns in real time. However, in order to define such patterns appropriately, we have needed to study the different attacks to set the condition values correctly.

5.3. CEP engine together with the linear regression predictor

To evaluate the integration of CEP with linear regression, we have analyzed the exactitude of our regressor, studied the exactitude of our predictor for the DoS scenario and checked whether our predictor is able to set predicted values for legitimate packages and the DoS scenario properly, as explained in this section.

Regarding the exactitude of our regressor, we can affirm that it works correctly, as shown in Figure 15. This situation is normal because the legitimate case is similar to the case used for training our regressor.

In the graphs in Figure 15 and 16 we can see blue squares and orange circles. A blue square represents the real size of the packets, and an orange circle represents the predicted values. Therefore, if our architecture works correctly, there will be circles in the center of the squares when the system is not under attack, but these circles will be out of the square when there are strange packets in our network.

Regarding the exactitude of our predictor in the DoS scenario, as depicted in Figure 16, many predictions failed. The difference between predicted values and real values is greater compared with Figure 15 since there are more packets and they are bigger.

Figure 12: UDP port scan detection.

Figure 13: Xmas port scan detection.

Figure 14: TCP/SYN port scan detection.

Figure 15: Legitimate MQTT predictions.

Figure 16: DoS MQTT predictions.

Table 1: Legitimate MQTT packet length prediction error.

Quartile	Quartile value	Number of packets
Q1	$x < 0.00166298$	4214
Q2	$0.00166298 < x < 0.01077055$	3648
Q3	$0.01077055 < x < 0.01086934$	7696
Q4	$0.01086934 < x$	1295

Table 2: DoS MQTT packet length prediction error.

Quartile	Quartile value	Number of packets
Q1	$x < 201.10600944$	27106
Q2	$358.89399057 < x < 201.10600944$	26977
Q3	$761.10600943 < x < 358.89399057$	26735
Q4	$761.10600943 < x$	26632

Tables 1 and 2 summarize the numerical results illustrated in Figures 15 and 16 respectively, which represent the distribution of the errors (real packet length against predicted packet length). While in the legitimate MQTT scenario the error values are small, these are much bigger in the the DoS scenario.

Finally, in regard to whether our predictor is able to set predicted values within the upper and lower limit for legitimate cases and for our DoS cases, we obtained the following results. The legitimate case prediction errors are illustrated in Figure 17. Note that the error margin of our predictor is computed using the error of our linear regression with our training dataset (in our case), and the prediction error is computed as the difference between the predicted value and the real value (in our case), and if a prediction error (represented with orange points) is over the error margin (represented with the blue line), there is a missprediction. In the previous figures we only compared the predicted value with the real one for our prediction. If our architecture works correctly, there will just be a few of orange points over the blue line when we have a legitimate case (this means that these packet values, represented with orange points, are very different compared with the predicted value). However, there should be many points over the line when we receive an attack, as this lets us detect these attacks correctly. In Figure 17 only 5 packets have been miss-predicted, but none of them are MQTT packets. This happens because our training dataset does not address packets

other than MQTT protocol ones and the regressor cannot deal with them. Such additional protocols cannot trigger our patterns anyway, and they are not particularly relevant to this paper.

Figure 18 shows the prediction errors when grouping the packets by protocol. The biggest errors are produced on ICMPv6 and ARP. This is because we do not have many packets of these protocols in our dataset and we are using linear regression, so the model does not give much importance to these packets. Table 3 presents the number of packets by protocol, showing that our predictor is worse when it needs to predict a very different value in packets with few samples. We should point out that this model is appropriate for our goal—detecting MQTT DoS—, but it could be replaced by a more complex one if we needed to make more exact predictions.

According to Figure 19, our regressor’s prediction is so far from the correct value when it receives an abnormal packet that, makes it possible to discover the malicious packets. This is exactly what we intended to achieve, i.e. we have a feature to distinguish legitimate packets from malicious packets. Of course, our architecture could be adapted to achieve other objectives. As an example, we could add a more complex model to predict different values. Note that the aim of this paper is to present a proof of concept demonstrating that our proposal can work appropriately by using *dynamic* patterns in which a model is in charge of calculating their prediction and margin values. In this way, the definition of dynamic pattern’ conditions is more exact than static pattern’ conditions; the latter being fixed and manually defined by domain experts.

Figure 20 highlights the main benefits of our novel proposal, namely; (1) the dynamic pattern is able to detect all the DoS packets; (2) the pattern has not been triggered by any legit packet; (3) there are no false positives or undetected DoS packets; (4) the value and the error margin for the pattern have not been defined manually; and so (5) the pattern conditions are adaptable at runtime.

As a result, we can affirm that the integration of the CEP engine with linear regression prediction permits the detection of security attacks in real time with a low error margin.

Figure 17: Legitimate MQTT margin predictions.

Figure 18: Errors by protocol.

Protocol	Number of packets
MQTT	8098
TCP	8105
ARP	481
DHCP	58
NTP	14
ICMPv6	59
IGMPv3	16
DNS	20
ICMP	2

Table 3: Number of packets by protocol for the legit case.

Figure 19: DoS MQTT margin predictions.

Figure 20: MQTT DoS predictions.

Besides, we have conducted a performance evaluation. Results have also demonstrated that the architecture performance is appropriate. Our normal scenario generated 17040 packets in 2 hours, in other words, 2.3 packets each second. In the worst case (TCP/SYN scan), 2006 packets were generated in 5 seconds, i.e., 401 packets per second. Our predictor just needed 0.47 seconds to pre-process the training data and fit with the legit scenario. In addition, this process can be done offline when necessary. Note that online training is not recommended in a cybersecurity scenario since an attacker could poison the data to modify the model so as to evade our IDS (Jagielski et al., 2018). In addition, Esper 7.1 is able to process up to 6 millions of events per second (EPS) (EsperTech, 2019b); thereby the number of packets in a normal scenario can be processed in near-real time. Therefore, we can conclude that our architecture can work with a massive network since Esper is able to scale easily.

5.4. CEP engine together with the linear regression predictor against non-modeled threats

In this section we evaluate the integration of CEP with linear regression against non-modeled attacks. A non-modeled attack is an attack that our

Table 4: Results of CEP and Linear Regression against non-modeled attacks.

Category	Attempts	Simple events	Anomaly complex events
Normal traffic (new)	7930	7930	0
Discwave	100000	700025	400027
Subfuzzing	4097	4097	4097
Mirai	126	787	504

system unknowns. This means that we have not previously defined a pattern to detect that attack and, thus, the predictor has not been trained against this attack.

Table 4 shows the number of attacks, the packets produced for each attack and the packets detected. Note that one attempt of attack can generate various packets, we say that we are detecting them if we detect at least 1 packet of the attack. As we can see, all attacks are detected and there are no false positives.

Since we can detect Mirai and its derived malware (Discwave and Subfuzzing attacks), and all of them are pure IoT attacks —Mirai is one of the more common attack against IoT systems Antonakakis et al. (2017))—, we can conclude that our pattern works appropriately. So, we are able to detect attacks that our architecture does not know in advance (they are not previously modeled).

Other interesting metrics are True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), True Positives (TP) and False Negatives (FN). True negative is a well predicted normal packet. False positive is a bad predicted normal packet (predicted as an anomalous packet). False negative is a bad predicted anomalous packet (predicted as a normal packet). True positive is a well predicted packet that is an anomalous packet. Moreover we will use 3 more metrics.

Precision:

$$\left(\frac{TP}{TP + FP}\right)$$

Recall:

$$\left(\frac{TP}{TP + FN}\right)$$

and F1 score:

$$2 \cdot \left(\frac{Precision \cdot Recall}{Precision + Recall}\right)$$

Table 5: Results of Linear Regression as predictor.

	Predicted as negative	Predicted as positive
Is negative	7930 (True negative)	0 (False positive)
Is positive	0 (False negative)	104223 (True positive)
Precision = 1	Recall = 1	F1-score= 1

All these metrics take values between 0 and 1. A high precision score shows that the model does not detect many false positives, a high recall shows that the model detect many threats. And F1 score is a general metric.

Table 5 shows that, in this context, we get a perfect score. Notice that we have not modeled Mirai, discwave and subfuzzing attacks. We can conclude that our proposal works very well in a real scenario against unknown attacks.

5.5. Proposal comparison

This section compares our proposal against other commercial alternatives.

First, we will use Snort, a well-known rule-based IDS, to detect MQTT attacks and scans. By using Snort, we need to define our rules to detect each attack. Snort have 2 main problems. One problem is that it cannot detect novel attacks, i.e. if Snort has not a specific rule for a particular attack, then it cannot detect such attack. The second problem is that the definition of Snort rules can be hard, since you need to indicate the exact byte for each field (for example, MQTT flags). Our proposal solves both problems. On the one hand, we can detect novel attacks, as previously shown. On the other, MEdit4CEP allows us to define patterns easily with a powerful graphical tool.

In this comparison we use these standard Snort rules: *'attack-responses.rules'*, *'backdoor.rules'*, *'bad-traffic.rules'*, *'chat.rules'*, *'ddos.rules'*, *'dns.rules'*, *'dos.rules'*, *'experimental.rules'*, *'exploit.rules'*, *'finger.rules'*, *'ftp.rules'*, *'icmp-info.rules'*, *'icmp.rules'*, *'imap.rules'*, *'info.rules'*, *'misc.rules'*, *'multimedia.rules'*, *'mysql.rules'*, *'netbios.rules'*, *'nntp.rules'*, *'oracle.rules'*, *'other-ids.rules'*, *'p2p.rules'*, *'policy.rules'*, *'pop2.rules'*, *'pop3.rules'*, *'rpc.rules'*, *'rservices.rules'*, *'scan.rules'*, *'smtp.rules'*, *'snmp.rules'*, *'sql.rules'*, *'telnet.rules'*, *'tftp.rules'*, *'virus.rules'*, *'web-attacks.rules'*, *'web-cgi.rules'*, *'web-client.rules'*, *'web-cold-fusion.rules'*, *'web-frontpage.rules'*, *'web-iis.rules'*, *'web-misc.rules'*, *'web-php.rules'*, *'x11.rules'*, *'community-sql-injection.rules'*, *'community-web-client.rules'*, *'community-web-dos.rules'*, *'community-web-iis.rules'*, *'community-web-misc.'*

Table 6: Our proposal against Snort.

Attack	Snort	Our proposal
TCP Syn scan	YES	YES
UDP port scan	YES	YES
Xmas port scan	YES	YES
MQTT DoS bigmsg	YES	YES
MQTT Discwave	NO	YES
MQTT subbfuzzing	NO	YES
MIRAI	YES	YES

rules', *'community-web-php.rules'*, *'community-sql-injection.rules'*, *'community-web-client.rules'*, *'community-web-dos.rules'* and *'community-web-iis.rules'*. Moreover, we have added a rule that is able to detect MQTT packets with more than 400 bytes of length; we use it to detect DoS attacks over MQTT.

Table 6 shows the advantages of our proposal compared to Snort. As we mentioned before, our proposal does not need specific rules for each attack; we can detect anomalous packets without a specific rule. Anyway, we could create new rules for each new anomaly. This is very interesting and allows us to filter attacks better. We can conclude that purely rule-based IDSs are dependent on the rules created from known threats; therefore, this kind of IDS is useless against non-known threats and new malware (Hammarberg, 2014; Holm, 2014).

In addition to evaluating the advantages of our approach against Snort, we have done a comparison with very popular IDS/SIEMs. Table 7 summarizes the different features, hardware requirements and performance of common IDS/SIEMs with respect to our proposal. In particular, we have evaluated the following features:

- F1: this provides rule-based detection.
- F2: this supports anomaly detection.
- F3: this provides full ARM support.
- F4: minimum core requirements.
- F5: minimum RAM requirements.
- F6: disk capacity requirements.

- F7: EPS/Gbps (depending on the developer).

As we can see, most approaches provide anomaly detection and rule-based detection, but their main problem is that they require too many hardware resources and are not compatible with ARM architectures (or any non x64/x86 architecture), so these cannot be deployed on an IoT context. In contrast, our proposal can be deployed in a Raspberry or other constrained devices. Regarding performance comparison, we have obtained the measurements from the IDS/SIEM official websites and we can conclude that our proposal has a better performance rate (measured in EPS) than other alternatives (Mathew, 2014).

Table 7 also shows that the options examined cannot be deployed on a Raspberry Pi 3 or other constrained devices, with the exception of Snort. Anyway, Snort does not provide anomaly detection features. In general, all these systems have a poor resource-performance relationship. In the past we performed several performance tests on an architecture integrating the Esper CEP engine with Mule ESB to provide COLLECT, a collaborative context-aware SOA for intelligent decision-making in the Internet of Things (Garcia-de Prado et al., 2017). A case study with several of the collaborative nodes was provided, and two nodes were deployed on two Raspberry Pi 3's (Model B), with 1 GB of RAM memory and a 2 GHz 64-bit quad-core ARMv8, with 8 GB and 16 GB cards, respectively. Even though the implementation was not focused on IoT attacks and did not provide prediction but only detection of relevant situations for the domain question, the results of the performance and stress evaluations carried out for the architecture are applicable in this paper. As we can see in Garcia-de Prado et al. (2017), the Raspberry Pi CPU throughput and memory usage remain within reasonable values maintaining the response time under 25 ms with a load of up to 300 events per second. Therefore, we can conclude that comparatively, taking into account the resources of the machine, the existing alternatives (Shah and Issac, 2018; AlienVault, 2019; Pechta, 2017; LogRhythm, 2019) have a poorer performance or require many more resources.

Therefore, these results show that our proposal is more adaptable and lighter than the other analyzed ones. Additionally, it can achieve the best performance compared with other SIEMs.

Moreover, we have measured the performance using a new dataset that has 1,424,903 simple events (as we mentioned, each simple event is a packet or a prediction). By using this dataset as input data, 404,627 complex events

Table 7: Our proposal against other IDS/SIEMs.

	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7
Snort	YES	NO	YES	-	-	-	70000 aprox
Splunk (Splunk, 2019)	YES	YES	NO	12 cores x64/x86	12 GB	600 GB	154000 low density
Qradar 1699 (IBM, 2019)	YES	YES	NO	4 cores x64	12 GB	256 GB	Up to 20000
LogRhythm LR-NM3400 (LogRhythm, 2017)	YES	YES	NO	12 cores x64/x86	64 GB	4 TB aprox	1 Gbps
Alienvault USM (AlienVault, 2018)	YES	YES	NO	8 cores x64/x86	24 GB	4.2 TB	Up to 2500
Our proposal (constrained device)	YES	YES	YES	< 4 cores ARM	< 1 GB	< 8GB	Up to 900 aprox
Our proposal (no constrained device)	YES	YES	YES	1 core (2Gh)	4 GB	-	Up to 120000

have been generated by the CEP engine. With this dataset, a mean processing rate of 39,565.96 events/second is obtained when the architecture is deployed on an Intel Core i7-8550U CPU @ 1.80GHz 1.99 GHz, 16GB RAM. Note that, although this is a high mean rate, this is not a peak rate, i.e. our architecture is capable of managing a higher traffic data rate. Thus, depending on the necessities of the system, we can deploy it on a resource constrained device, on a computer or on a large server, obtaining a reasonably good performance, in accordance with the device used.

5.6. CEP with support vector regression

As previously mentioned, linear regression works adequately in our context. However, to demonstrate that our system can manage other regressors, we have conducted other experiments integrating it with the Epsilon-Support Vector Regression, a kernel-based regressor that allow us to probe other model (Basak et al., 2007).

In particular, we have used Mirai, subfuzzing and discwave as anomalous packets/events, and added more normal packets as normal behaviour packets. Tables 8 and 9 show that all attacks have been correctly detected again, and only 2 false positives have been obtained. Even though these results obtained by using the Support Vector Regression (SVR) regressor are worse than those by using the lineal one, they are still good enough for the IoT context.

We can, therefore, conclude that our architecture can work with different regression models.

Table 8: Results of CEP and SVR against non-modeled attacks.

Category	Attempts	Simple events	Anomaly complex events
Normal traffic (new2)	7930	7930	2
Discwave	100000	700025	323584
Subfuzzing	4097	4097	4097
Mirai	126	787	787

Table 9: Results of SVR as predictor.

	Predicted as negative	Predicted as positive
Is negative	7928 (True negative)	2 (False positive)
Is positive	0 (False negative)	104223 (True positive)
Precision = 0.99998	Recall = 1	F1-score= 0.99998

Table 10: Linear regression against SVR in our system.

	Linear regression	SVR
Recall	1	1
Precision	1	0.99998
F1-score	1	0.99998

Table 10 shows the difference of linear regression against SVR in our context. As we can see, in this scenario (and with our features selection) SVR with a polynomial kernel works worse than linear regression. We have a lower precision (0.99998), which means that a few legit packets have been detected as anomalous packets with SVR. It is important to point out that these results are dependent on the feature selection and the scenario to be protected. With another scenario, SVR could provide better results than linear regression.

6. Related work

In recent years, ML has been used to improve the security of computer systems. As an example, a set of techniques for each security attack class has been proposed by Xiao et al. (2018).

Another interesting survey is the one conducted by Al-Garadi et al. (2018), providing a taxonomy scheme of ML and deep learning for IoT security. This paper discusses whether ML is more appropriate than deep learning, and vice versa, for each security issue. Additionally, this work explains the importance of choosing where the ML algorithm is executed. Li et al. (2018) propose a theoretical approach integrating ML into an edge computing scheme; however, real-world applications are not analyzed. Kulkarni and Venayagamoorthy (2009) implement an ML algorithm for securing a wireless sensor network against DoS attacks.

Thus, there are many papers that propose the use of ML for tackling IoT security issues, but they do not address the challenge of managing dynamic patterns. We propose a novel model combining ML and CEP in which an ML algorithm calculates heuristic values from observations in order to define event pattern conditions dynamically. These predicted values allow the modeling of flexible patterns for detecting IoT security attacks, avoiding many false positive alerts, which are very common on ML-based IDS.

There are a few papers that propose the integration of ML with CEP as a differentiating advantage. For instance, Raj et al. (2017) defines a CEP-based approach for detecting meaningful patterns in smart buildings. Although the authors state that the CEP engine could be optimized by using efficient learning algorithms, this is considered as future work.

Baldoni et al. (2015) present an architecture combining CEP and ML algorithms designed using hidden Markov models to detect anomalous behaviors of a safety-critical system, thus predicting a system failure before it happens. While this work focuses on safety-critical detection, our proposal tackles security-critical detection (attacks) in IoT networks. Furthermore, their model is state-based and this could be a problem for attack detection because an attack can be registered at any time (our system does not need to be in a specific state for the attack to be detected).

In addition, Petersen et al. (2017) add an ML technique together with CEP to the detection engine of a Mobile Ad Hoc Network Intrusion Detection System (MANET IDS), which is capable of recognizing DoS attacks as well as re-writing IDS rules on the fly. Similarly to our work, their work proposes the integration of ML and CEP for detecting attacks. However, while Petersen et al.'s work focuses on the MANET protocol, our work focuses on MQTT. Moreover, they propose SVM, but this algorithm requires finding a specific kernel, a task that is hard if the domain expert does not know the data distribution. SVM requires tuning other parameters such as gamma, degree, etc. Our proposal does not need to know the data distribution or to find the correct parameters. Unlike that work, we propose a complete architecture for detecting different types of IoT security attacks (not only DoS ones) in real time. Additionally, our architecture provides a model-driven graphical tool for event pattern definition and automatic code generation, hiding all implementation details from domain experts.

Therefore, taking into account the evaluation of known IDS/SIEMs provided in Section 5.5, together with the description of other research proposals described in this section, we can affirm that currently there are no tools or proposals which can be deployed on devices with limited resources, such as a Raspberry Pi, and which can detect and predict IoT unknown attacks in real time. However, when deploying the architecture on a more powerful device, we obtain a significantly good performance and, to the best of our knowledge, there are no existing model-driven proposals integrating CEP and ML for detecting IoT security attacks and threats. Thus, we are providing a unique graphical tool which will permit user, who do not necessarily have

any programming knowledge to graphically design and automatically deploy means for attack detection.

7. Conclusions and future work

In this work, we have proposed and implemented an intelligent architecture combining CEP and ML that is capable of easily managing dynamic patterns for detecting IoT security attacks. Dynamic patterns have some event properties that depend on the values that are automatically computed by a linear regression and SVR predictor, a component that is also proposed in this paper.

Thanks to the use of the MEdit4CEP model-driven tool, domain experts (non experts in CEP and ML) can graphically model these patterns, which are then automatically transformed in Esper EPL code and deployed into the CEP engine at runtime.

The integration of CEP and ML has several benefits over using pure CEP without dynamic prediction. Firstly, we do not need to find correct fields, values and margins manually to compare features or event properties, since we make use of dynamic prediction. Secondly, if the network environment changes, our architecture lets the CEP engine quickly adapt to the new scenario. Therefore, using linear regression and SVR to calculate expected pattern values enables the detection of new attacks in real time.

In order to validate our proposal, the architecture has been applied to an IoT network prototype constructed in a hospital with the aim of detecting attacks (TCP, UDP and Xmas port scans, and DoS) made by a malicious device. The results confirm that this architecture works effectively if it uses a model that can be adapted to the context.

As future work, we plan to define more event patterns for detecting other types of attacks. Additionally, we will extend the predictor with the ability to automatically find which packet features are essential for our domain context. Moreover, we will automate alerts of “necessary training” when our network changes significantly.

Acknowledgments

Boubeta-Puig would like to thank the High-Performance Networks and Architectures Research Group for their hospitality when visiting them at the University of Castilla-La Mancha, Spain, where part of this work was developed.

Funding

This work was supported by the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities and the European Union FEDER Funds [grant numbers FPU 17/02007, RTI2018-093608-B-C33, RTI2018-098156-B-C52 and RED2018-102654-T]. This work was also supported by the JCCM [grant number SB-PLY/17/180501/ 000353].

References

- Al-Garadi, M. A., Mohamed, A., Al-Ali, A., Du, X., and Guizani, M. (2018). A Survey of Machine and Deep Learning Methods for Internet of Things (IoT) Security. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1807.11023*.
- AlienVault (2018). Usm appliance deployment requirements. <https://www.alienvault.com/documentation/usm-appliance/sys-reqs/hardware-spec.htm>. Accessed 16 October 2019.
- AlienVault (2019). Alienvault usm appliance. <https://www.alienvault.com/documentation/usm-appliance/initial-setup/ossim-installation.htm>. Accessed 16 October 2019.
- Andrea, I., Chrysostomou, C., and Hadjichristofi, G. (2015). Internet of things: Security vulnerabilities and challenges. In *2015 IEEE Symposium on Computers and Communication (ISCC)*, pages 180–187.
- Antonakakis, M., April, T., Bailey, M., Bernhard, M., Bursztein, E., Cochran, J., Durumeric, Z., Halderman, J. A., Invernizzi, L., Kallitsis, M., Kumar, D., Lever, C., Ma, Z., Mason, J., Menscher, D., Seaman, C., Sullivan, N., Thomas, K., and Zhou, Y. (2017). Understanding the mirai botnet. In *26th USENIX Security Symposium (USENIX Security 17)*, pages 1093–1110, Vancouver, BC. USENIX Association.
- Atzori, L., Iera, A., and Morabito, G. (2010). The internet of things: A survey. *Comput. Netw.*, 54(15):2787–2805.
- Baldoni, R., Montanari, L., and Rizzuto, M. (2015). On-line failure prediction in safety-critical systems. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 45:123–132.

- Basak, D., Pal, S., and Patranabis, D. C. (2007). Support vector regression. *Neural Information Processing*.
- Boubeta-Puig, J., Ortiz, G., and Medina-Bulo, I. (2014). Approaching the Internet of Things through Integrating SOA and Complex Event Processing. In Sun, Z. and Yearwood, J., editors, *Handbook of Research on Demand-Driven Web Services: Theory, Technologies, and Applications*, IGI Global book series Advances in Web Technologies and Engineering (AWTE), pages 304–323. IGI Global.
- Boubeta-Puig, J., Ortiz, G., and Medina-Bulo, I. (2015). MEdit4CEP: A model-driven solution for real-time decision making in SOA 2.0. *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 89:97–112.
- Buczak, A. L. and Guven, E. (2016). A survey of data mining and machine learning methods for cyber security intrusion detection. *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, 18(2):1153–1176.
- EsperTech (2019a). Esper - Complex Event Processing. <http://www.espertech.com/esper/>. Accessed 6 November 2019.
- EsperTech (2019b). Esper - Complex Event Processing Scalability. <http://www.espertech.com/2019/03/07/6-million-events-per-second/>. Accessed 6 November 2019.
- Gad, R., Boubeta-Puig, J., Kappes, M., and Medina-Bulo, I. (2012). Hierarchical Events for Efficient Distributed Network Analysis and Surveillance. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International Workshop on Adaptive Services for the Future Internet and 6th International Workshop on Web APIs and Service Mashups*, WAS4FI-Mashups '12, pages 5–11, Bertinoro, Italy. ACM.
- Gad, R., Kappes, M., Boubeta-Puig, J., and Medina-Bulo, I. (2013). Employing the CEP Paradigm for Network Analysis and Surveillance. In *Proceedings of The Ninth Advanced International Conference on Telecommunications*, pages 204–210, Rome, Italy. IARIA.
- Garcia-de Prado, A., Ortiz, G., and Boubeta-Puig, J. (2017). COLLECT: COLLaborativE ConText-aware service oriented architecture for intelligent decision-making in the Internet of Things. *Expert Systems with Applications*, 85:231–248.

- Gharibian, F. and Ghorbani, A. A. (2007). Comparative study of supervised machine learning techniques for intrusion detection. In *Fifth Annual Conference on Communication Networks and Services Research (CNSR '07)*, pages 350–358.
- Gubbi, J., Buyya, R., Marusic, S., and Palaniswami, M. (2013). Internet of things (iot): A vision, architectural elements, and future directions. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 29(7):1645 – 1660.
- Hammarberg, D. (2014). The best defenses against zero-day exploits for various-sized organizations. *SANS Institute InfoSec Reading Room*, 21.
- Holm, H. (2014). Signature based intrusion detection for zero-day attacks: (not) a closed chapter? In *2014 47th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences*, pages 4895–4904.
- IBM (2019). System requirements for virtual appliances. https://www.ibm.com/support/knowledgecenter/en/SS42VS_7.3.2/com.ibm.qradar.doc/c_qradar_ha_vrt_ap_reqs.html. Accessed 16 October 2019.
- Jagielski, M., Oprea, A., Biggio, B., Liu, C., Nita-Rotaru, C., and Li, B. (2018). Manipulating machine learning: Poisoning attacks and countermeasures for regression learning. In *2018 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*, pages 19–35.
- Kayacik, H. G., Zincir-Heywood, A. N., and Heywood, M. I. (2005). Selecting features for intrusion detection: A feature relevance analysis on kdd 99 intrusion detection datasets. In *Proceedings of the third annual conference on privacy, security and trust*, volume 94, pages 1723–1722.
- Kousiouris, G., Akbar, A., Sancho, J., Ta-shma, P., Psychas, A., Kyriazis, D., and Varvarigou, T. (2018). An integrated information lifecycle management framework for exploiting social network data to identify dynamic large crowd concentration events in smart cities applications. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 78:516–530.
- Kulkarni, R. V. and Venayagamoorthy, G. K. (2009). Neural network based secure media access control protocol for wireless sensor networks. In *2009 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks*, pages 1680–1687.

- Li, H., Ota, K., and Dong, M. (2018). Learning IoT in Edge: Deep Learning for the Internet of Things with Edge Computing. *IEEE Network*, 32(1):96–101.
- LogRhythm (2017). Product overview network monitor. <https://logrhythm.com/pdfs/datasheets/lr-network-monitor-datasheet.pdf>. Accessed 16 October 2019.
- LogRhythm (2019). Logrhythm netmon freemium. <https://logrhythm.com/products/logrhythm-netmon-freemium/>. Accessed 6 November 2019.
- Luckham, D. (2012). *Event Processing for Business: Organizing the Real-Time Enterprise*. John Wiley & Sons, New Jersey, USA.
- Mathew, A. (2014). Benchmarking of complex event processing engine - esper. <https://www.cse.iitb.ac.in/internal/techreports/reports/TR-CSE-2014-61.pdf>. Accessed 16 October 2019.
- Meidan, Y., Bohadana, M., Shabtai, A., Guarnizo, J. D., Ochoa, M., Tippenhauer, N. O., and Elovici, Y. (2017). Profiliot: A machine learning approach for iot device identification based on network traffic analysis. In *Proceedings of the Symposium on Applied Computing, SAC '17*, pages 506–509, New York, NY, USA. ACM.
- Mihescu, M. C. (2011). Classification of learners using linear regression. In *2011 Federated Conference on Computer Science and Information Systems (FedCSIS)*, pages 717–721.
- MuleSoft (2019). Mule ESB. <https://www.mulesoft.com/resources/esb/what-mule-esb>. Accessed 27 March 2019.
- Narudin, F. A., Feizollah, A., Anuar, N. B., and Gani, A. (2016). Evaluation of machine learning classifiers for mobile malware detection. *Soft Computing*, 20(1):343–357.
- NumPy (2019). NumPy. <http://www.numpy.org/>. Accessed 27 March 2019.
- OASIS (2019). MQTT Version 5.0. <http://docs.oasis-open.org/mqtt/mqtt/v5.0/mqtt-v5.0.html>. Accessed 27 March 2019.

- Oracle (2019). Virtualbox. <https://www.virtualbox.org/>. Accessed 27 March 2019.
- Ozay, M., Esnaola, I., Yarman Vural, F. T., Kulkarni, S. R., and Poor, H. V. (2016). Machine learning methods for attack detection in the smart grid. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Networks and Learning Systems*, 27(8):1773–1786.
- Pandas (2019). Pandas. <https://pandas.pydata.org/>. Accessed 27 March 2019.
- Papazoglou, M. (2012). *Web services and SOA: principles and technology*. Pearson Education, Essex, England; New York, 2 edition.
- Papazoglou, M. and Heuvel, W. V. D. (2006). Service-oriented design and development methodology. *Int. J. Web Eng. Technol.*, 2(4):412–442.
- Pechta, J. (2017). What are the limitations/restrictions for qradar community edition? <https://developer.ibm.com/answers/questions/411519/what-are-the-limitationsrestrictions-for-qradar-co/>. Accessed 16 October 2019.
- Petersen, E., To, M. A., and Maag, S. (2017). A novel online CEP learning engine for MANET IDS. In *2017 IEEE 9th Latin-American Conference on Communications (LATINCOM)*, pages 1–6.
- Python Software Foundation (2019). Python.
- Raj, R., Sahu, R. K., Chaudhary, B., Prasad, B. R., and Agarwal, S. (2017). Real time complex event processing and analytics for smart building. In *2017 Conference on Information and Communication Technology (CICT)*, pages 1–6.
- Raynovich, R. (2017). What is the growth rate of iot markets?. <http://www.futurion.com/articles/news/iot-growth-rate/2017/04>. Accessed 15 March 2019.
- Rondeau, C. M., Temple, M. A., and Lopez, J. (2019). Industrial iot cross-layer forensic investigation. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Forensic Science*, 1(1):e1322.

- Scikit-learn (2019). Scikit-learn. <https://scikit-learn.org/stable/>. Accessed 27 March 2019.
- Shah, S. and Issac, B. (2018). Performance comparison of intrusion detection systems and application of machine learning to snort system. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 80:157–170.
- Splunk (2019). Reference hardware. <https://docs.splunk.com/Documentation/Splunk/8.0.0/Capacity/Referencehardware>. Accessed 16 October 2019.
- Tan, Z., Jamdagni, A., He, X., Nanda, P., and Liu, R. P. (2011). Denial-of-service attack detection based on multivariate correlation analysis. In Lu, B.-L., Zhang, L., and Kwok, J., editors, *Neural Information Processing*, pages 756–765, Berlin, Heidelberg. Springer Berlin Heidelberg.
- Taylor, H., editor (2009). *Event-driven architecture: how SOA enables the real-time enterprise*. Addison-Wesley, Upper Saddle River, NJ.
- Terroso-Saenz, F., Gonzalez-Vidal, A., Ramallo-Gonzalez, A. P., and Skarmeta, A. F. (2019). An open IoT platform for the management and analysis of energy data. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 92:1066–1079.
- Vegh, L. and Miclea, L. (2016). Complex event processing for attack detection in a cyber-physical system. In *2016 IEEE International Conference on Automation, Quality and Testing, Robotics (AQTR)*, pages 1–6.
- Wireshark (2019). Wireshark. <https://www.wireshark.org/>. Accessed 17 March 2019.
- Xiao, L., Wan, X., Lu, X., Zhang, Y., and Wu, D. (2018). IoT Security Techniques Based on Machine Learning: How Do IoT Devices Use AI to Enhance Security? *IEEE Signal Processing Magazine*, 35(5):41–49.
- Zimmermann, H. (1980). OSI Reference Model - The ISO Model of Architecture for Open Systems Interconnection. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, 28(4):425–432.